

Nonlocal Scheme for Peridynamic Systems with Damped wave dynamics

Jingkai Wang*

Abstract

Nonlocal schemes are employed across a range of topics in peridynamics and diffusion. This project undertakes a comprehensive review and investigation of the theoretical analysis and numerical implementation of nonlocal finite difference and finite element methods for the simulation of a variety of model problems. We construct and verify the asymptotically compatible nonlocal schemes in one dimension with respect to different boundary conditions before implementing the method to approximate the nonlocal Green's function. Then, we derive the convergence and error estimates under norms for the damped wave equation using the nonlocal bilinear form. We observe the effects of the damping constant on the behavior of the damped wave curves. To better illustrate the robustness of the nonlocal scheme, we simulate bond breaks using a simplified peridynamic bond network with viscous damping and the nonlocal finite difference model. We display the damaged areas and crash stretches over time. The effects of the damping constant and the comparison with the local operator are also analyzed.

1 Introduction

The nonlocal schemes are constructed by introducing additional variables and appropriate integral operators. The classical nonlocal scheme cannot approximate the correct local Laplacian operator, while the asymptotically compatible operator is introduced in [2] and [7], using the second momentum. The nonlocal scheme is leveraged to split the Green's function into a singular part and a regular part, demonstrating the robustness of the nonlocal scheme in simulating non-smooth problems, as interpreted in [8]. In the report, we analyze and implement the nonlocal finite difference method in the damped wave equation, which is studied in [9]. As the damping constant increases, the effect of wave propagation is dominated by the diffusion term, showing the decrease of oscillations in our experiment. The error estimates of the nonlocal damped wave equation are derived analytically, inspired by [2] and [7].

Finally, we studied the damped wave equation for the peridynamic system to measure bond breaking in two-dimensions to show the robustness of the nonlocal scheme, as displayed in [3]. The classical wave equation is intrinsically energy-conserving, a property that is generally not preserved in physical frameworks such as peridynamics and materials science; therefore, we introduce a simplified peridynamic bond network with viscous damping. The crash propagation and the extension of the damaged areas are demonstrated. As the damping constant increases, there is a slower extension of bond-breaking along the breaking line, while the damaging zone becomes broader.

*Department of Applied Physics and Applied Mathematics, Columbia University (jw4673@columbia.edu)

2 Review of the One-dimensional Nonlocal Finite Difference Method

We review a nonlocal finite difference scheme for the one-dimensional Laplacian. Unlike the local scheme, the nonlocal scheme incorporates distant points within a finite horizon ([2] and [7]). The weight function is designed to approximate the Laplacian with the correct coefficient. We analyze convergence under periodic and Dirichlet boundary conditions and then use the nonlocal scheme to approximate the Green's function.

2.1 A nonlocal integral formulation

The nonlocal finite-difference scheme is utilized to approximate the Laplacian operator in the bounded domain. The basic idea is to represent the second derivative in terms of points inside the open ball $B_\delta(x)$, where δ denotes the horizon parameter. By defining the symmetric kernel function γ_δ , the nonlocal diffusion operator is given by

$$(L_\delta u)(x) = \int_{-\delta}^{\delta} \gamma_\delta(|s|) (u(x+s) - 2u(x) + u(x-s)) ds. \quad (1)$$

To ensure that the continuous nonlocal scheme can approximate the local scheme as $\delta \rightarrow 0$, one simple construction is to define $\rho_\delta(s) = s^2 \gamma_\delta(|s|)$,

$$\int_{-\delta}^{\delta} s^2 \gamma_\delta(|s|) ds = 1,$$

and then

$$(L_\delta u)(x) = 2 \int_0^\delta \rho_\delta(s) \frac{u(x+s) - 2u(x) + u(x-s)}{s^2} ds. \quad (2)$$

To illustrate the construction, We first consider the one-dimensional Poisson problem. The spatial domain $(0, 1)$ is discretized by a uniform mesh of size $h = \frac{1}{N}$. The horizon δ is suggested to be proportional to the mesh size h , say $\delta = rh$. The corresponding subintervals of $(0, \delta]$ are defined as

$$I_m = ((m-1)h, mh] \quad (3)$$

Since the nonlocal operator couples the points in the domain with their neighbors at a distance of up to δ , we adopt an extension in the set Ω_δ :

$$\Omega_\delta = (-\delta, 0) \cup (1, 1 + \delta). \quad (4)$$

To compute the integral, we can apply the finite difference scheme. And the nonlocal discrete scheme is given by

$$\begin{aligned} (L_\delta^h u)(x_i) &= 2 \sum_{m=1}^r \int_{I_m} \frac{u_{i+m} - 2u_i + u_{i-m}}{(mh)^2} \rho_\delta(s) ds \\ &= \sum_{m=1}^r \left(2 \int_{I_m} \rho_\delta(s) ds \right) \frac{u_{i+m} - 2u_i + u_{i-m}}{(mh)^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Then, the numerical problem becomes solving the linear system, and elements of the stiffness matrix A are given by

$$A_{ij} = \begin{cases} -2 \sum_{m=1}^r \frac{2}{(mh)^2} \int_{(m-1)h}^{mh} \rho_\delta(s) ds & \text{if } i = j, \\ \frac{2}{(|i-j|h)^2} \int_{(|i-j|-1)h}^{|i-j|h} \rho_\delta(s) ds & \text{if } 0 < |i-j| \leq r, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

In order to analyze the order of accuracy in terms of mesh size and horizon, the authors in [7] established two theorems: 1, 2.

Theorem 1. Let $\Omega \subset R^d$ and suppose the exact solution $u \in C^4(\overline{\Omega \cup \Omega_{\mathcal{I}}})$. Assume that the kernel function γ_δ is non-negative, symmetric, and satisfies the second moment condition, say

$$\int_{B_\delta(0)} |s|^2 \gamma_\delta(s) ds = d. \quad (7)$$

If the spatial domain is discretized into a Cartesian mesh with mesh size h , and the coefficient matrix is a M -matrix, then the nonlocal discrete scheme provides the second order approximation of the nonlocal continuous operator:

$$|L_{h,\delta}u(x_i) - L_\delta u(x_i)| \leq C_1 \|D^4 u\|_\infty h^2. \quad (8)$$

Theorem 2. Suppose the following conditions are satisfied: $\Omega \subset R^d$ and $u \in C^4(\overline{\Omega \cup \Omega_{\mathcal{I}}})$; γ_δ is non-negative, symmetric, and satisfies the second moment condition. Then it follows that

$$|\mathcal{L}_\delta u(x) - \mathcal{L}_0 u(x)| \leq C_2 \|u^{(4)}\|_\infty \delta^2. \quad (9)$$

2.2 Nonlocal scheme for the 1D Poisson problem with periodic BCs

We study the convergence behavior of the scheme for the Poisson problem with periodic boundary conditions. In this setting, the nonlocal interactions do not require the extended layer, since the values outside the domain are identified with the values inside the domain due to periodicity. The periodic Poisson's problem is given by

$$\begin{cases} -u''(x) = f(x), & x \in [0, 1], \\ u(x+1) = u(x). \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

As a simple example, we consider a constant kernel function γ_δ that depends only on the horizon parameter δ :

$$\gamma_\delta(s) = \frac{3}{2\delta^3} \quad (11)$$

Then, the nonlocal discrete scheme in equation (5) is computed as

$$(L_\delta^h u)(x_i) = \sum_{m=1}^r \frac{3m^2 - 3m + 1}{r^3 m^2 h^2} (u_{i+m} - 2u_i + u_{i-m}). \quad (12)$$

We consider the case that $\delta = rh$. For different values of r , the nonlocal scheme results in various finite difference stencils:

Corollary 1. By choosing $r = 1, 2, 4$, the nonlocal scheme in equation (12) reduces to the following stencils:

$$(L_\delta^h u)(x_i) = \frac{1}{h^2} (u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1}), \text{ for } r = 1; \quad (13)$$

$$(L_\delta^h u)(x_i) = \frac{1}{h^2} \left[\frac{1}{8} (u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1}) + \frac{7}{32} (u_{i+2} - 2u_i + u_{i-2}) \right], \text{ for } r = 2; \quad (14)$$

$$(L_\delta^h u)(x_i) = \frac{1}{h^2} \left[\frac{1}{64} (u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1}) + \frac{7}{256} (u_{i+2} - 2u_i + u_{i-2}) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{19}{576} (u_{i+3} - 2u_i + u_{i-3}) + \frac{37}{1024} (u_{i+4} - 2u_i + u_{i-4}) \right], \text{ for } r = 4. \quad (15)$$

To implement the nonlocal finite difference scheme, we choose $f(x) = 4\pi^2 \sin(2\pi x)$ for the periodic problem (16). We discretize the Laplacian operator by the nonlocal operator L_δ^h with $\delta = rh$. The numerical solution is obtained by solving the linear system $A_{ij}u(x_j) = f(x_j)$, and the errors are computed with respect to the exact solution in the l^∞ -norm and l^2 -norm. The numerical results in figure 1 show that, for fixed r , the nonlocal solution exhibits second-order convergence to the exact solution. Increasing the value of r would vertically shift the error curves but would preserve the order of accuracy.

(a) Comparison between numerical solution and exact solution

(b) Convergence rate for $r = 1, 2, 4$

Figure 1: Convergent behavior of 1D Poisson's problem with periodic BCs, $f(x) = 4\pi^2 \sin(2\pi x)$.

2.3 Nonlocal scheme for the 1D Poisson problem with Dirichlet BCs

Here, we consider the 1D Poisson problem subject to the homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions:

$$\begin{cases} -u''(x) = f(x), & x \in [0, 1], \\ u(0) = u(1) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

In the nonlocal scheme, the evaluation of the operator requires points outside the spatial domain $\Omega = (0, 1)$ when $\delta = hr$ and $r > 1$. Unlike the periodic problem, we impose a zero boundary constraint on the extended domain.

$$u = 0, \quad x \in (-\delta, 0) \cup (1, 1 + \delta). \quad (17)$$

Recall that the zero boundary constraint results in a mismatch for the points around the boundary when $u'(x) \neq 0$ for $x \in \partial\Omega$.

Theorem 3. *Suppose that $\delta = hr$ and $r > 1$. Generally, if $u'(x) \neq 0$ for $x \in \partial\Omega$, then the nonlocal scheme is not second order accurate.*

Proof. We consider the reference point $x_1 = h$ and examine its associated nonlocal stencil interaction. By invoking a Taylor series expansion, we obtain

$$u_{1+m} - 2u_1 + u_{1-m} = u'(0)h(m-1) + \frac{u''(0)}{2}h^2(m^2 + 2m - 1) + O(h^3),$$

We then evaluate the nonlocal discrete operator at the point x_1 :

$$(L_\delta^h u)(x_1) = \sum_{m=1}^r \frac{m^3 - (m-1)^3}{r^3 m^2 h^2} \left[ah(m-1) + \frac{bh^2}{2}(m^2 + 2m - 1) + O(h^3) \right]$$

Therefore, we conclude that the truncation error is of order $O(\frac{1}{h})$. Consequently, in the vicinity of the boundary, the scheme fails to satisfy the consistency requirement.

$$L_\delta^h u(x_1) - u''(x_1) = \frac{1}{r^3} \left(\sum_{m=1}^r \frac{(m^3 - (m-1)^3)(m-1)}{m^2} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{h} u'(0) + O(1).$$

In the vicinity of the boundary points, the scheme fails to satisfy the consistency conditions, and as a consequence the overall order of convergence deteriorates, despite maintaining second-order accuracy in the interior of the domain. \square

However, as previously stated, if the nonlocal solution u_δ is sufficiently smooth in the domain $\Omega \cap \Omega_I$, for example, if the compatibility condition $u'(0) = u'(1)$ holds, then the nonlocal scheme is still second order accurate. As shown in figure 2, the nonlocal and local schemes both exhibit second-order accuracy.

(a) Comparison between numerical solution and exact solution

(b) Convergence rate for $r = 1, 2, 4$

Figure 2: Convergent behavior of 1D Poisson's problem with Dirichlet BCs, $f(x) = x^4(1-x)^4$.

2.4 Nonlocal Green's function

One application of the nonlocal scheme is approximating the Green's function, the singular inverse of the PDE solution, which allows for the numerical construction of this function, as presented in [7]. Consider the Poisson's problem with periodic boundary conditions in equation (16); the corresponding periodic nonlocal Green's function is given by

$$-\mathcal{L}_\delta G(x) = \delta(x) - \frac{1}{|\Omega|}, \quad \text{subject to } \int_{\Omega} G(x) dx = 0. \quad (18)$$

To numerically approximate the Green's function, we split it into the singular part g_0 and the regular part u_1 :

$$G(x) = g_0(x) + u_1(x). \quad (19)$$

The singular part is not computed with numerical schemes; instead, we use a discrete delta approximation. As h tends to zero, the singular part can be approximated.

$$g_0(x) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{C_\delta} \left(\delta_h(x) - \frac{1}{|\Omega|} \right), \quad \text{where } C_\delta = \int_{-\delta}^{\delta} \rho_\delta(|s|) ds, \quad (20)$$

$$\text{and } \delta_h(x_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{h} & \text{if } i = 0 \text{ (source node),} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

As for the regular part, we solve the numerical system for the smooth remainder using the nonlocal scheme \mathcal{L}_δ :

$$-\mathcal{L}_\delta u_1(x) = \frac{1}{C_\delta} \rho_\delta(x) - \frac{1}{|\Omega|}, \quad (21)$$

which can be converted into the linear system: $L\mathbf{u}_1 = \mathbf{f}$, where L is the nonlocal stiffness matrix and the function

$$f_i = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{C_\delta} \rho_\delta(x_i) - \frac{1}{|\Omega|} & \text{if } |x_i| \leq \delta, \\ -\frac{1}{|\Omega|} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

When solving the linear system, the zero-mean constraint is required to ensure the uniqueness of the numerical solution:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (\mathbf{u}_1)_i = 0. \quad (23)$$

(a) Decomposition of Green's function into singular, regular, and hybrid parts

(b) Comparison of nonlocal and local Green's functions

Figure 3: Numerical approximation of the two-dimensional Green's function with the mesh resolution $N = 32$ and horizon parameter $r = 2$.

Figure 4: Comparison of the nonlocal and local Green's functions along the cross-section $y = 0$. The nonlocal numerical approximation with $r = 2$ aligns strongly with the local Green's function around $x = 0$.

And the final nonlocal Green's function is computed as

$$G_i = (g_0)_i + (u_1)_i - \text{mean}(g_0 + u_1). \quad (24)$$

To demonstrate the validity of the nonlocal scheme in approximating the nonlocal Green's function, we implement the numerical approximations of the Green's function. As shown in 3(a), the robustness of the nonlocal finite difference method is displayed, particularly for the regular part. A sharp singularity appears at the origin, and the regular part of the Green's function is split. In figure 3(b), the nonlocal Green's function is compared with the local one. The error plot indicates that the difference between the nonlocal and local operators is minimal and is confined primarily to the vicinity of the origin. Furthermore, the Green's function along the cross-section $y = 0$ is depicted in Figure 4, demonstrating an accurate approximation within the interior area.

3 Damped wave equation with the nonlocal finite element method

The damped wave equation is leveraged to model the dissipative behavior in many physical systems, as shown in [4] and [9]. In realistic physical systems, waves do not propagate indefinitely. Physical mechanisms such as friction, viscous dissipation, and material damping reduce wave energy. The damped wave equation provides a rigorous framework for describing energy decay and the corresponding attenuation of wave amplitude over time and space. In this section, we define the one-dimensional damped wave equation by

$$\begin{cases} (1 - \alpha)\partial_{tt}u(x, t) + \alpha\partial_t u(x, t) - \Delta u(x, t) = f(x, t), & x \in \Omega, t \in (0, T], \\ u(x, t) = 0, & x \in \Omega_{\mathcal{I}}, t \in [0, T], \\ u(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad \partial_t u(x, 0) = u_1(x), & x \in \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

The damped wave equation coincides with the heat equation as $\alpha = 1$; and reduces to the undamped wave equation as $\alpha = 0$. To analyze the nonlocal finite element scheme for the damped wave equation, we first study the convergence and error estimates for the heat equation and the undamped wave equation. And for the nonlocal finite element method, we use the nodal basis

$$\mathcal{L}_\delta u(x) = \int_0^\delta \frac{u(x-s) - 2u(x) + u(x+s)}{s^\alpha} s^\alpha \gamma_\delta(s) ds \quad (26)$$

$$= \sum_{m=0}^{r+1} \int_0^\delta \frac{u(x-s) - 2u(x) + u(x+s)}{s^\alpha} \phi_m^1(s) s^\alpha \gamma_\delta(s) ds. \quad (27)$$

where $\{\phi_m(s)\}_{m=0}^{r+1}$ represents the piecewise linear hat basis functions.

3.1 Convergence and error estimates of the heat equation

The authors in [1] and [6] have studied the convergence and error estimates of Galerkin finite element approximations for the local heat equation. The operator is second-order accurate in the L^2 norm and first-order accurate in the H^1 norm. Building on that, we analyze the convergence behavior and error estimates of the nonlocal solutions of the heat equation as the horizon parameter decreases. We aim to analyze the convergence and error estimates for the nonlocal heat equation. The nonlocal heat equation can be written as

$$\begin{cases} \partial_t u_\delta(x, t) + L_\delta u_\delta(x, t) = f(x, t), & x \in \Omega, t \in (0, T], \\ u_\delta(\cdot, t) \text{ is periodic in } x, \quad \int_\Omega u_\delta(x, t) dx = 0, & t \in [0, T], \\ u_\delta(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad \int_\Omega u_0(x) dx = 0, \quad \int_\Omega f(x, t) dx = 0 \ (\forall t \in [0, T]). \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ be a bounded domain. Consider a symmetric nonnegative kernel $\gamma_\delta(x, y)$; then the corresponding bilinear form is given by

$$a_\delta(w, v) := \frac{1}{2} \iint_{\Omega} (w(x) - w(y))(v(x) - v(y)) \gamma_\delta(x, y) dx dy. \quad (29)$$

We impose volume periodic conditions w that are periodic on Ω and define

$$V_{\text{per}, \delta} := \left\{ v \in L^2(\Omega) : v \text{ is periodic in } \Omega, \int_{\Omega} v dx = 0, a_\delta(v, v) < \infty \right\}, \quad (30)$$

equipped with the energy norm

$$\|v\|_\delta^2 := a_\delta(v, v). \quad (31)$$

Authors in [2] established the symmetry, coercivity, and time-dependence of the nonlocal bilinear form, and some of these results are stated in Theorem 4.

Theorem 4. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a bounded domain and let γ_δ be a symmetric nonnegative kernel; then the bilinear form a_δ satisfies the following properties:*

- *The form is symmetric:*

$$a_\delta(u, v) = a_\delta(v, u) \quad \forall u, v \in V_{\text{per}, \delta}, \quad (32)$$

- *The form is coercive when $\int_{\Omega} v dx = 0$:*

$$\|v\|_\delta^2 := a_\delta(v, v) \geq c_\delta \|v\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \quad \forall v \in V_{\text{per}, \delta}, \quad (33)$$

- *For any time-dependent functions $u, v \in C^1([0, T]; V_{\text{per}, \delta})$, the energy norm satisfies*

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \|u\|_\delta^2 = a_\delta(u, u_t). \quad (34)$$

To estimate the heat equation with periodic boundary conditions, the nonlocal heat equation can be written as

$$\partial_t u_\delta(x, t) + L_\delta u_\delta(x, t) = f(x, t), \quad x \in \Omega, t \in (0, T], \quad (35)$$

with u_δ periodic on Ω and initial data $u_\delta(\cdot, 0) = u_{0, \delta}$. The weak formulation is given by

$$(\partial_t u_\delta(t), v) + a_\delta(u_\delta(t), v) = (f(t), v) \quad \forall v \in V_{\text{per}, \delta}, \forall t \in (0, T]. \quad (36)$$

Let $V_h \subset V_{\text{per}, \delta}$ be a finite-dimensional subspace; then our goal is to find $u_{\delta, h} : [0, T] \rightarrow V_h$ such that

$$(\partial_t u_{\delta, h}(t), v_h) + a_\delta(u_{\delta, h}(t), v_h) = (f(t), v_h) \quad \forall v_h \in V_h, \forall t \in (0, T]. \quad (37)$$

Du et al. [2] established the orthogonality of the nonlocal scheme's projection. For each fixed t , the elliptic projection $\pi_h^\delta : V_{\text{per}, \delta} \rightarrow V_h$ satisfies the property that

$$a_\delta(\pi_h^\delta w(t) - w(t), v_h) = 0. \quad (38)$$

To estimate the truncation error, we define

$$e_h(t) := u_{\delta, h}(t) - u_\delta(t), \quad \eta_h(t) := u_{\delta, h}(t) - \pi_h^\delta u_\delta(t), \quad \zeta(t) := u_\delta(t) - \pi_h^\delta u_\delta(t), \quad (39)$$

Authors in [7] and [8] studied the asymptotically compatible nonlocal finite element schemes for the Laplacian operator and discussed the stability of these approximations. In Theorem 5, we analyzed the inequalities between the approximation errors.

Theorem 5. *We can demonstrate the property that*

$$\|\eta_h(t)\|_\delta^2 + \int_0^t \|\eta_{h,t}(s)\|_\delta^2 ds \leq \|\eta_h(0)\|_\delta^2 + \int_0^t \|\zeta_t(s)\|_\delta^2 ds. \quad (40)$$

Proof. Subtracting (36) from (37) with $v = v_h \in V_h$ yields

$$(e_{h,t}(t), v_h) + a_\delta(e_h(t), v_h) = 0 \quad \forall v_h \in V_h. \quad (41)$$

According to the orthogonality in (38), we have

$$(\eta_{h,t}(t), v_h) + a_\delta(\eta_h(t), v_h) = (\zeta_t(t), v_h) \quad \forall v_h \in V_h. \quad (42)$$

Suppose that $v_h = \eta_{h,t}(t)$ in (42); it follows that

$$\|\eta_{h,t}(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + a_\delta(\eta_h(t), \eta_{h,t}(t)) = (\zeta_t(t), \eta_{h,t}(t)). \quad (43)$$

Hence

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \|\eta_h(t)\|_\delta^2 + \|\eta_{h,t}(t)\|^2 = (\zeta_t(t), \eta_{h,t}(t)). \quad (44)$$

Applying Cauchy–Schwarz and Young’s inequality to the inner product, we obtain

$$\frac{d}{dt} \|\eta_h(t)\|_\delta^2 + \|\eta_{h,t}(t)\|^2 \leq \|\zeta_t(t)\|^2. \quad (45)$$

Integrating (45) from 0 to t gives

$$\|\eta_h(t)\|_\delta^2 + \int_0^t \|\eta_{h,t}(s)\|^2 ds \leq \|\eta_h(0)\|_\delta^2 + \int_0^t \|\zeta_t(s)\|^2 ds. \quad (46)$$

Thus, we proved the property. \square

As demonstrated in [2] and [7], the nonlocal scheme is asymptotically compatible as long as the nonlocal solution of PDEs $u_\delta \in C^4(\Omega)$ is considered. Then, Theorem 6 demonstrates the approximation properties of the elliptic projection under L^2 norm and H^1 norm.

Theorem 6 (Approximation Properties of the Elliptic Projection). *Let $\pi_h^\delta : V_{per,\delta} \rightarrow V_h$ be the elliptic projection operator defined by*

$$a_\delta(\pi_h^\delta u, v_h) = a_\delta(u, v_h) \quad \forall v_h \in V_h. \quad (47)$$

Assume V_h consists of piecewise linear continuous functions. If the solution u_δ and its time derivative $u_{\delta,t}$ are sufficiently regular and $u_\delta \in C^4(\Omega)$, then the projection error $\zeta(t) := u_\delta(t) - \pi_h^\delta u_\delta(t)$ satisfies the following estimates for all $t \in [0, T]$:

$$\|\zeta(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + h \|\zeta(t)\|_\delta \leq C h^2 \|u_\delta(t)\|_{H^2(\Omega)}, \quad (48)$$

$$\|\zeta_t(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C h^2 \|u_{\delta,t}(t)\|_{H^2(\Omega)}, \quad (49)$$

where C is a constant independent of the mesh size h .

Theorem 7 (Semi-discrete Error Estimate). *Let u_δ be the solution to the nonlocal heat problem (36) and let $u_{\delta,h}$ be the solution to the semi-discrete problem (37). Assume the initial data is chosen such that $u_{\delta,h}(0) = \pi_h^\delta u_\delta(0)$. Then, satisfying the assumptions of Theorem 6, the finite element approximation satisfies the global L^2 -error estimate:*

$$\|u_{\delta,h}(t) - u_\delta(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C_T h^2 \quad \text{for all } t \in [0, T], \quad (50)$$

where C_T depends on the final time T and the regularity of u_δ , but is independent of h .

Sketch of Proof. We decompose the error as $e_h = u_{\delta,h} - u_\delta = \eta_h - \zeta$, where $\eta_h = u_{\delta,h} - \pi_h^\delta u_\delta$ and $\zeta = u_\delta - \pi_h^\delta u_\delta$.

Using the error equation for η_h and inserting the estimate (49) into the integrated energy argument, we obtain the bound on the discrete evolution error:

$$\|\eta_h(t)\|_\delta \leq C_T h^2. \quad (51)$$

Applying the nonlocal Poincaré inequality $\|v\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C_P \|v\|_\delta$, we have $\|\eta_h(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C_T h^2$. Finally, by the triangle inequality and (48):

$$\|e_h(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \|\eta_h(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + \|\zeta(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C_T h^2 + C h^2 \|u_\delta\|_{H^2} \leq C'_T h^2. \quad (52)$$

\square

3.2 Convergence and error estimate of the wave equation

Then we consider the nonlocal scheme for the wave equation. Suppose the bilinear form $a_\delta(\cdot, \cdot)$ as in equation (29) and the space of functions $V_{\text{per},\delta}$ as in (30). The nonlocal wave equation with periodic boundary conditions is given by

$$\begin{cases} \partial_{tt}u_\delta(x, t) + L_\delta u_\delta(x, t) = f(x, t), & x \in \Omega, t \in (0, T], \\ u_\delta(\cdot, t) \text{ is periodic in } x, \quad \int_\Omega u_\delta(x, t) dx = 0, & t \in [0, T], \\ u_\delta(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad \partial_t u_\delta(x, 0) = u_1(x), & x \in \Omega, \\ \int_\Omega u_0(x) dx = 0, \quad \int_\Omega u_1(x) dx = 0, \quad \int_\Omega f(x, t) dx = 0 \quad (\forall t \in [0, T]). \end{cases} \quad (53)$$

For the weak nonlocal wave formation, we see that $u_\delta : [0, T] \rightarrow V_{\text{per},\delta}$ satisfies

$$(u_{\delta,tt}(t), v) + a_\delta(u_\delta(t), v) = (f(t), v) \quad \forall v \in V_{\text{per},\delta}, \quad \forall t \in (0, T]. \quad (54)$$

Let $V_h \subset V_{\text{per},\delta}$ denote the finite element space. For the discrete nonlocal solution, we aim to find $u_{\delta,h} : [0, T] \rightarrow V_h$ such that

$$(u_{\delta,h,tt}(t), v_h) + a_\delta(u_{\delta,h}(t), v_h) = (f(t), v_h) \quad \forall v_h \in V_h, \quad \forall t \in (0, T], \quad (55)$$

with initial data

$$u_{\delta,h}(0) = u_{0,h}, \quad u_{\delta,h,t}(0) = u_{1,h} \in V_h.$$

By applying the elliptic projection to the function $\pi_h^\delta : V_{\text{per},\delta} \rightarrow V_h$, it follows that

$$a_\delta(\pi_h^\delta w(t), v_h) = a_\delta(w(t), v_h) \quad \forall v_h \in V_h.$$

For the nonlocal solution u_δ satisfying $\int_\Omega u_\delta dx = 0$, define

$$e_h(t) := u_{\delta,h}(t) - u_\delta(t), \quad \eta_h(t) := u_{\delta,h}(t) - \pi_h^\delta u_\delta(t), \quad \zeta(t) := u_\delta(t) - \pi_h^\delta u_\delta(t), \quad (56)$$

Then $e_h = \eta_h - \zeta$. According to the definition of π_h^δ , the projection rule is satisfied:

$$a_\delta(\zeta(t), v_h) = 0, \quad \zeta_t = u_{\delta,t} - \pi_h^\delta u_{\delta,t}, \quad \zeta_{tt} = u_{\delta,tt} - \pi_h^\delta u_{\delta,tt}.$$

From equations (54) and (55) with $v = v_h \in V_h$, it can be derived that

$$(\eta_{h,tt}(t), v_h) + a_\delta(\eta_h(t), v_h) = (\zeta_{tt}(t), v_h) \quad \forall v_h \in V_h. \quad (57)$$

Theorem 8 (Energy inequality for the wave error). *Consider the discrete energy*

$$\mathbf{E}(t) := \frac{1}{2} \left(\|\eta_{h,t}(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \|\eta_h(t)\|_\delta^2 \right).$$

Then, $\forall t \in [0, T]$, the energy function satisfies the inequality that

$$\mathbf{E}(t) \leq C_T \left(\mathbf{E}(0) + \int_0^t \|\zeta_{tt}(s)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 ds \right), \quad (58)$$

where $C_T > 0$ is independent of h .

Sketch of proof. Set $v_h = \eta_{h,t}(t)$ in (57) and then

$$(\eta_{h,tt}, \eta_{h,t}) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \|\eta_{h,t}\|^2, \quad a_\delta(\eta_h, \eta_{h,t}) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \|\eta_h\|_\delta^2,$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{E}(t) = (\zeta_{tt}(t), \eta_{h,t}(t)) \leq \frac{1}{2} \|\zeta_{tt}(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|\eta_{h,t}(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \leq \frac{1}{2} \|\zeta_{tt}(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \mathbf{E}(t).$$

Using the Grönwall's lemma, we derive the desired inequality. \square

Assume the elliptic projection π_h^δ satisfies the approximation properties of Theorem 6 for u_δ , $u_{\delta,t}$, and $u_{\delta,tt}$, i.e. for $t \in [0, T]$,

$$\begin{aligned}\|\zeta(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + h \|\zeta(t)\|_\delta &\leq Ch^2 \|u_\delta(t)\|_{H^2(\Omega)}, \\ \|\zeta_{tt}(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} &\leq Ch^2 \|u_{\delta,tt}(t)\|_{H^2(\Omega)}.\end{aligned}\tag{59}$$

Consider the initial condition

$$u_{\delta,h}(0) = \pi_h^\delta u_\delta(0), \quad u_{\delta,h,t}(0) = \pi_h^\delta u_{\delta,t}(0),\tag{60}$$

then $\eta_h(0) = \eta_{h,t}(0) = 0$ and $\mathbf{E}(0) = 0$. Deriving from the energy inequality and the bound of ζ_{tt} , it can be computed that

$$\|\eta_{h,t}(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + \|\eta_h(t)\|_\delta \leq C_T h^2.$$

Moreover, from equation (59), we also derive that $\|\zeta(t)\|_\delta \leq Ch$. Therefore,

$$\|e_h(t)\|_\delta \leq \|\eta_h(t)\|_\delta + \|\zeta(t)\|_\delta \leq C_T h^2 + Ch \leq C_T h.$$

By the nonlocal Poincaré inequality for the mean-zero space, we introduce Theorem 9.

Theorem 9 (Semi-discrete error for the nonlocal wave equation). *Assume the periodic mean-zero compatibility conditions $\int_\Omega u_0 dx = \int_\Omega u_1 dx = 0$ and $\int_\Omega f(\cdot, t) dx = 0$ for all $t \in [0, T]$. Then, suppose that u_δ solves the nonlocal wave problem (54) with sufficient regularity $u_\delta \in W^{2,\infty}(0, T; H^2(\Omega))$, and $u_{\delta,h}$ denotes the semi-discrete solution in equation (55). With the choice of initial data in equation (60), there exists a constant $C_T > 0$ such that for all $t \in [0, T]$,*

$$\|u_{\delta,h}(t) - u_\delta(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C_T h^2,\tag{61}$$

$$\|u_{\delta,h,t}(t) - u_{\delta,t}(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C_T h^2,\tag{62}$$

$$\|u_{\delta,h}(t) - u_\delta(t)\|_\delta \leq C_T h.\tag{63}$$

We verify that the nonlocal finite element scheme achieves second-order accuracy in the L^2 norm.

3.3 Introduction to the Nonlocal Damped Wave Equation

In this section, we extend the nonlocal framework to the damped wave equation, which is a combination of the wave equation and the heat equation. The system of the damped wave equation is given by equation (25). The strong form of the nonlocal damped wave equation with periodic boundary conditions can be derived as

$$(1 - \alpha) \partial_{tt} u_\delta(x, t) + \alpha \partial_t u_\delta(x, t) - L_\delta u_\delta(x, t) = f(x, t).\tag{64}$$

where $\alpha > 0$ denotes the damping coefficient, and \mathcal{L}_δ represents the nonlocal diffusion operator. Consider the test function $v \in V_{\text{per},\delta}$. In the variational problem, we aim to find $u_\delta : [0, T] \rightarrow V_{\text{per},\delta}$ such that for all $v \in V_{\text{per},\delta}$ and $t \in (0, T]$, it can be derived that

$$(1 - \alpha)(\partial_{tt} u_\delta, v) + \alpha(\partial_t u_\delta, v) + a_\delta(u_\delta, v) = (f, v).\tag{65}$$

The damped wave equation exhibits a decay in the associated energy functional over time. We define the energy $\mathbf{E}_d(t)$ as the sum of the kinetic energy and the nonlocal potential energy:

$$\mathbf{E}_d(t) = \frac{1 - \alpha}{2} \|\partial_t u_\delta\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|u_\delta\|_\delta^2.\tag{66}$$

The derivative of the energy function can be derived as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{E}_d(t) + \alpha \|\partial_t u_\delta(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 = (f(t), \partial_t u_\delta(t)).\tag{67}$$

In particular, when $f \equiv 0$, $\mathbf{E}'_d(t) = -\alpha \|\partial_t u_\delta(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \leq 0$, the energy decays over time. We employ a spatial discretization scheme analogous to the one used for the wave and heat equations. For the semi-discrete problem, $u_{\delta,h}(t) \in V_h$ satisfies

$$(1 - \alpha)(\partial_{tt} u_{\delta,h}, v_h) + \alpha(\partial_t u_{\delta,h}, v_h) + a_\delta(u_{\delta,h}, v_h) = (f, v_h) \quad \forall v_h \in V_h. \quad (68)$$

As presented before, we can leverage Young's inequality to show that

$$E'_{d,h}(t) + \frac{\alpha}{2} \|\eta_{h,t}\|_{L^2}^2 \leq C (\|\zeta_{tt}\|_{L^2}^2 + \|\zeta_t\|_{L^2}^2).$$

Therefore, by using the same definitions in equation (56), we have

$$E_{d,h}(t) \leq E_{d,h}(0) + C \int_0^t (\|\zeta_{tt}(s)\|^2 + \|\zeta_t(s)\|^2) ds.$$

The error estimates of the nonlocal damped wave equation are demonstrated in Theorem 10.

Theorem 10 (Semi-discrete error estimate for the damped wave equation). *Suppose that $u_\delta \in W^{2,\infty}(0, T; H^2(\Omega))$ and the mean-zero compatibility conditions for u_0, u_1, f are satisfied. Then we say that there exists $C_T^d > 0$ such that for all $t \in [0, T]$,*

$$\begin{aligned} \|u_{\delta,h}(t) - u_\delta(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} &\leq C_T^d h^2, \\ \|\partial_t u_{\delta,h}(t) - \partial_t u_\delta(t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} &\leq C_T^d h^2, \\ \|u_{\delta,h}(t) - u_\delta(t)\|_\delta &\leq C_T^d h. \end{aligned}$$

The nonlocal finite element method for the damped wave equation shows second order accuracy in terms of L^2 norm and first order accuracy in terms of H^1 norm.

Figure 5: Time evolution of the 1D nonlocal damped wave equation ($r = 2$) under different damping coefficients α . The plots show the transition from underdamped oscillatory behavior ($\alpha = 0.05$) to overdamped decay ($\alpha = 0.95$).

In this section, we analyze the damped wave equation using finite element schemes, focusing on its energy behavior for different damping constants. We also compare the convergence of the local and nonlocal schemes. We set $f = 0$ and $u(x, 0) = \sin(2\pi x)$.

To demonstrate the transition from the hyperbolic equation to the parabolic equation by the variation of α , we leverage different damping coefficients ranging from 0.05 to 0.95 to show the behavior of the damped

(a) $t = 0.0$ (Initial Condition)

(b) $t = 0.5$

(c) $t = 1.0$

(d) $t = 1.5$

(e) $t = 2.0$

Figure 6: Snapshots of the solution $u(x,t)$ at different time steps with the damping coefficient $\alpha = 0.5$ and mesh size $h = 1/20$. We compare the nonlocal approximation against the exact solution and the local approximation.

Figure 7: Convergence analysis of the damped wave equation with $\alpha = 0.5$ and $T = 2.0$. The log-log plot demonstrates the L^2 and L^∞ errors for the local and nonlocal finite difference schemes in terms of the mesh size h . Both nonlocal and local scheme exhibit second-order convergence.

wave equation in one-dimension. According to figure 5, the curves exhibit oscillatory behavior as time progresses, and The oscillatory amplitude varies with different α . For small damping values, for instance, $\alpha = 0.05, 0.1, 0.2$, the solutions exhibit oscillations whose amplitude grows very large as time goes on. The temporal decay rate is comparatively low, which is consistent with the wave equation with weak dissipation. Conversely, as α increases, The oscillatory behavior is suppressed by the diffusion process, resulting in a progressively increasing decay rate and a correspondingly more rapid convergence of the function to zero. The behavior illustrates how the damped wave equation models physical dissipation and energy decay for different damping constants.

We then analyze the accuracy and convergent behavior of the nonlocal finite difference method with time discretization in approximating the exact solution. Figure 6 shows solution snapshots at different times with $\alpha = 0.5$ and mesh size $h = 1/20$. The comparison shows that the nonlocal approximation has higher error and a lower peak amplitude than the local scheme. Figure 7 shows that both the local and nonlocal schemes are second-order accurate; they differ only in their initial error.

4 Damped Wave dynamics for the Peridynamic system with Bond Breaking

Since we are dealing with smooth functions in the damped wave equation, it is hard to distinguish the robustness of the local scheme from that of the nonlocal scheme. Here, we want to leverage the ideas of the nonlocal finite difference method in solving the peridynamic models. The authors in [5] emphasize the principles in solving the PDE systems consisting of the nonlocal part in space. Furthermore, the authors in [3] illustrate the well-posed peridynamical system with bond-breaking rules for simulating crack propagation in brittle materials. In this section, we aim to introduce the effects of the damped wave dynamics and damping coefficients on a simplified peridynamic model for formulating bond breaking. To capture peridynamic mechanics, we would use a weighted nonlocal model in space instead of the Laplacian operator, and the added damping constant is used to measure the potential energy decay. The internal force at the material

point x is obtained through the bond interactions inside the finite horizon. The conical kernel ω_δ describes the bond strength as a function of distance. The damage factor μ represents the stiffness multiplier for each bond: smaller μ indicates a weaker, damaged bond. The model of the damped wave and internal force is given by

$$(1-\alpha)\partial_{tt}u(x,t) + \alpha\partial_t u(x,t) = \int_{B_\delta(x)} \mu(x,\hat{x},t) \kappa \omega_\delta(|\hat{x}-x|) (u(\hat{x},t) - u(x,t)) d\hat{x}, \quad x \in \Omega, t \in (0, T], \quad (69)$$

where $\kappa > 0$ is the stiffness scale and the conical kernel ω_δ is defined as

$$\omega_\delta(r) = \max\left(0, 1 - \frac{r}{\delta}\right), \quad (70)$$

Since our model requires both spatial nonlocal interactions and historical dependence, we define the stretch measure given by

$$S(x,\hat{x},t) = \frac{\sqrt{|\hat{x}-x|^2 + (u(\hat{x},t) - u(x,t))^2} - |\hat{x}-x|}{|\hat{x}-x|}. \quad (71)$$

Then we also assume the historical maximum to be

$$S^*(x,\hat{x},t) = \max_{0 \leq s \leq t} S(x,\hat{x},s). \quad (72)$$

To represent the bond breaking criteria, the damage parameter $\mu(S^*)$ is employed as a quantitative measure for evaluating the bond breaking rules. The piecewise linear damage parameter is defined as

$$\mu(S^*) = \begin{cases} 1, & S^* \leq S_0, \\ \frac{S_1 - S^*}{S_1 - S_0}, & S_0 < S^* < S_1, \\ 0, & S^* \geq S_1, \end{cases} \quad (73)$$

Once the stretch reaches S_1 , the material is broken at that point. The thresholds S_0 and S_1 depend on the interaction pairs. For the top and bottom boundaries, we use the Dirichlet boundary conditions, where

$$u(x,t) = +A(t) \text{ on } y = +L_y, \quad u(x,t) = -A(t) \text{ on } y = -L_y, \quad \text{for } A(t) = U_{\max} \min\left(1, \frac{t}{T_{\text{ramp}}}\right).$$

An initial crack $\mu(x,\hat{x},0) = 0$ is defined on the line segment $\{(x,0) : x \in [x_a, x_b]\}$.

4.1 Numerical implementation for the peridynamic model

We consider the two dimensional rectangular region as the domain Ω , and each grid has a size $h_x h_y$. The horizon for the nonlocal model is suggested to be $\delta = r \min\{h_x, h_y\}$. According to the previous nonlocal finite difference method, the midpoint quadrature scheme yields

$$(1-\alpha)\partial_{tt}u_i(t) + \alpha\partial_t u_i(t) = \sum_{j \in F_i} \mu_{ij}(t) \kappa \omega_\delta(r_{ij}) V(u_j(t) - u_i(t)). \quad (74)$$

In terms of displacement, the stretch measure and historical maximum are updated as

$$S_{ij}^{n+1} = \frac{\sqrt{r_{ij}^2 + (u_j^{n+1} - u_i^{n+1})^2} - r_{ij}}{r_{ij}}, \quad (S_{ij}^*)^{n+1} = \max\{(S_{ij}^*)^n, S_{ij}^{n+1}\}. \quad (75)$$

we adopt a damped velocity-Verlet scheme for time discretization:

$$a_i(u, v, \mu) = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \left(\sum_{j \in F_i} \mu_{ij} \kappa \omega_\delta(r_{ij}) V(u_j - u_i) - \alpha \partial_t u_i \right). \quad (76)$$

For $a^n = a(u^n, v^n, \mu^n)$ and $a^{n+1} = a(u^{n+1}, v^{n+\frac{1}{2}}, \mu^{n+1})$, the numerical solution is updated by

$$v^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = v^n + \frac{\Delta t}{2} a^n, \quad u^{n+1} = u^n + \Delta t v^{n+\frac{1}{2}}, \quad v^{n+1} = v^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} a^{n+1}, \quad (77)$$

Figure 8: Snapshots of displacement u and damage indicators for different damping parameters α .

4.2 Numerical Solutions and Comparison

We implement and analyze the numerical solution for simulating bond breaking with respect to time using the nonlocal finite difference scheme. The variation of the damage indices and crack propagation over time is numerically computed, and we compare the behaviors for different damping constants α .

Figure 8 demonstrates snapshots of the displacement and damage indicators to show the bond-breaking behaviors of our model of the simplified peridynamic bond network with viscous damping. For the fixed damping constant α , we can observe the stretching of the damaged area as time increases. As the boundary loading reaches the plateau at around $t = 0.05$, we notice that the softening zone is extending along the bond-breaking zone. As the damping constant increases, wave propagation is suppressed and dominated by the diffusion process. In our simulations, it leads to a slower extension of the bond-breaking along the x -axis, while the damaging zone becomes broader and stronger along the y -axis.

Figure 9: Local baseline model at $t = 0, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20$.

Then we compare the nonlocal operator with the local operator in Figure 9. For the local scheme, we leverage the local operator for simulation. Although the bond-breaking line is growing, we observe that the local scheme cannot characterize the damaging zone in a physically meaningful way. Thus, in the example of the damped wave equation and peridynamic system for measuring bond breaking, the nonlocal scheme is more robust than the local scheme.

5 Conclusion and future work

In this report, we investigate the nonlocal schemes for numerically approximating the Laplacian operator. We introduce the nonlocal finite difference scheme and the nonlocal finite element scheme. For the nonlocal finite difference scheme, we introduce the one-dimensional case, where the asymptotically compatible nonlocal scheme is reviewed to fit the Laplacian operator. Additionally, we consider difference boundary conditions: for periodic boundary conditions, the nonlocal scheme exhibits second order accuracy; while for the Dirichlet boundary conditions, the nonlocal scheme has some constraints near the boundary and the extended domain. We then demonstrate the numerical construction of the nonlocal scheme to approximate the Green's function, which is split into a singular part and a regular part. The effort demonstrated the robustness of the nonlocal finite difference method.

Based on the nonlocal bilinear form, we estimated the convergent behavior and error when adding the time. In particular, we considered the heat equation and the wave equation. We leveraged the elliptic projection rules and Young's inequality to verify the error estimate of the nonlocal finite element method under L^2 norm and H^1 norm, showing second and first order accuracy, respectively. Later, we used the nonlocal finite element scheme on the damped wave equation, where the wave propagation would be dominated by the diffusion process as the damping constant increases. We also show that the effects of the local and nonlocal schemes cannot be distinguished for some smooth problems.

The nonlocal scheme is extremely robust for some non-smooth problems, which is the reason we study the peridynamic system with damped waves to measure bond breaking in two-dimensional materials. By introducing a simplified peridynamic bond network with viscous damping, we observe crash propagation and the extension of the damaged areas. As the damping constant increases, we observe a slower extension of bond-breaking along the breaking line, while the damaging zone becomes broader and stronger in the orthogonal direction.

For future work, we aim to develop and analyze the nonlocal finite difference method and finite element method, with an emphasis on stability, convergence, and robustness. We are also eager to apply the nonlocal schemes to a series of topics in mathematical physics, such as peridynamic models and materials science. For the peridynamic system with the damped wave equation, we want to further study the effect of the damping coefficient on the behavior of the bond-breaking process and analyze the reasons. Another modification is that increasing the damping constant reduces wave propagation in our model. We fix the coefficient of the wave term and vary only the coefficient of the heat equation to analyze the damping constant's effect on the peridynamic model.

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